

Kinetic and Mechanistic Studies on Non-isothermal Decomposition of Potassium Dioxalatocuprate(II) Dihydrate

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The non-isothermal decomposition of potassium dioxalatocuprate(II) dihydrate has been studied in air. The TG data have been analyzed for mechanistic models and kinetic parameters of dehydration and decomposition steps.

Oxalato complexes of transition metals have been studied¹, but their thermal studies have escaped proper attention. The object of the present investigation is to study the non-isothermal decomposition of potassium dioxalatocuprate(II) dihydrate in air, minimizing the local factors, and the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of dehydration and decomposition of the complex.

Results and Discussion

The decomposition of the compound takes place in three distinct steps² (Table 1). The residue of the complex at 433 K turned to the original color in contact with air,

TABLE 1—DIFFERENT STEPS OF THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF $K_2[Cu(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$

Steps	% Mass-loss Obs./ (Calcd.)	Peak in DTG (K)
(1) $K_2[Cu(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O \xrightarrow{373-433\text{ K}}$	10.12 (10.17)	403
(2) $K_2[Cu(C_2O_4)_2] \xrightarrow{493-673\text{ K}}$	40.52 (40.71)	543
(3) $K_2CO_3 \frac{1}{2}Cu_2O \xrightarrow{733-873\text{ K}}$ $K_2O \cdot CuO$	50.72 (50.89)	783

which supports the dehydration of lattice water in first step. In the second step, the residue at 673 K was treated with water, filtered and the red coloured precipitate that was obtained showed to be cuprous oxide. The residue at 873 K in the third step gave black precipitate of cupric oxide when its aqueous solution was filtered. The α -T plots of the above steps did not show presence of period of induction³. However, the mechanistic analysis⁴ suggests that the rate-controlling process assumes random nucleation involving one nucleus and one particle during dehydration of the cop-

per(II) complex. The same mechanism is adopted by the first step of decomposition. The least square regression (R^2) values indicate the best-fit mechanistic data which are given in Table 2.

The data of order of reaction (b), activation energy (E_a), frequency factor (A), activation entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) as obtained by Freeman-Carroll⁵ and Zsako⁶ methods are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE KINETIC PARAMETERS OF $K_2[Cu(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$

Freeman-Carroll		Zsako			
b	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	b	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	A s ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
0.69	14.321932	1	28.2	1.84×10^{13}	1.575437

The entropy values support the decomposition steps suggested above and they also indicate that there is appreciable rearrangement among various degrees of freedom, which is likely in such mechanism of decomposition.

Experimental

Sample of freshly prepared⁷ potassium dioxalatocuprate(II) dihydrate was powdered and heated in air in a Stanton Red-Croft TG-750 thermobalance with a heating rate of 1/6 K s⁻¹. The TG-graph obtained were used for mechanistic analysis of the dehydration and decomposition steps. The values of kinetic parameters, like energy of activation (E_a), order of reaction (b), frequency factor (A) and activation entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) were approximated, using the Freeman-Carroll⁵ and Zsako⁶ equations.

For mechanistic study, the α -T data were first recorded and then they were fed to computer LOTUS-123 package⁸.

TABLE 2—BEST-FIT MECHANISTIC DATA (R^2 VALUES)

Compd.	One dim.	Two dim. cyl.sym.	Three dim. sph.sym.	Three dim.	Random Nucle.	Phase bou.	Phase bou. sph. sym.
				React.			
$K_2[Cu(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$	0.8946	0.9157	0.9431	Extr.	I, II, III	cyl.sym.	0.9386
				0.9258	0.9505		
					0.9546		
					0.9474		
$K_2[Cu(C_2O_4)_2]$	0.5149	0.5655	0.6248	0.5783	0.6789	0.5672	0.6022
					0.6404		
					0.6404		
					0.5935		

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